

This README file briefly introduces the four data files included in this archive.

1. “Table_S1_loc_reloc_bootstrap_fms_2021_submit.csv”
This csv-format file corresponds to the Supporting Material Table S1, providing a full list of earthquake catalog, relocation results, and resolved focal mechanism solutions.
2. “wd_wells_location.csv”
This csv-format table lists the location of wells used in this study. Note that the UWI (unique well identifier) is a label to mark well locations. The latitude and longitude of each well are given in Columns #4–#5.
3. “wd_well_inj.csv”
This csv-format table lists injection operation parameters used in this study. The operation record is collected per month, in which the injected volume and operating hours are reported. The well location is available in File #2, using the UWI or license number.
4. “waveform_raw.zip”
This archive file consists seismic waveforms of all 187 earthquakes used in this study for hypocentral relocation and focal mechanism inversion. Every event has a directory named after its origin time in the format of “yyyymmdd.hhmmss”. In each directory, the waveform files are provided in Seismic Analysis Code (SAC) format.